

Optimizing Spatial Design for Enhanced Productivity in Contemporary Office

Suyash Yadav

Department of Architecture,
Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam Technical University, Lucknow

Abstract- In today's knowledge economy, optimizing employee productivity is crucial for organizational success. This study delves into the relationship between spatial planning and design elements within office spaces and their impact on user productivity. It aims to unravel how design choices influence worker performance and establish a set of parameters for designing workspaces that maximize productivity. The research commences with a historical examination of office spaces, tracing their evolution to identify key design elements that have emerged over time. Following this, the study establishes a framework of parameters to analyse the effectiveness of these elements in contemporary work environments. To explore the potential of these parameters in real-world settings, the research employs case studies, examining how various office layouts integrate these design principles. Through a comparative analysis of work environments based on the established parameters, the study develops a set of design recommendations intended to optimize user performance and maximize productivity. The findings of this research can be used to guide the design of future office spaces, fostering a productive and successful workforce, and ultimately contributing to organizational prosperity.

Index Terms-office, productivity, office planning, office layout, office wellbeing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Background

In an office setting, productivity encompasses both efficiency and effectiveness. It serves as a detector for determining how effectively resources could be allocated to achieve an organization's goals. Rather than getting things done faster, workplace productivity is more broadly defined as enhancing the working environment to encourage higher performance and employee wellbeing.

It can be defined as employing the same input to generate greater output or as utilizing fewer resources to achieve the same objective. Given that human capital is the most valuable resource in an office setting, this concept is crucial. By optimizing employee productivity, a business can boost earnings, cut expenses, and obtain a competitive advantage in the industry.

We are spending more and more time in traditionally designed office spaces, the need to address health, productivity, and wellbeing in these spaces has grown with time. Stress does have a very negative effect on the efficiency and well-being of employees as well as on their performance.

According to a Canadian survey of 25,000 full-time employees, 57% reported high-stress levels. Company spends a major amount on their employees, so to keep them relaxed and productive is one of the most important tasks for the companies as well as the designer. A working environment in the office that boosts productivity can harness a huge rate of return.

Figure 1: productivity diagram

Figure 2 productivity diagram.

The need for productivity in an office space is driven by several factors:

Economic Efficiency: Productivity is directly affecting a company's bottom line. Effective use of time and resources allows companies to invest in growth opportunities and better returns for stakeholders.

Employee Engagement: A productive work environment is often an engaging one. When employees see that their efforts are being contributed to companies' success, they are more likely to be motivated and get committed to their work.

Quality of Work: Productivity is not just about quantity; it's also about the quality of work produced. An emphasis on productivity motivates staff to strive for excellence, which improves output, client satisfaction, and services.

Innovation and Growth: A productive office space is a growth platform for innovation. They provide employees with the structure and support they need to experiment, take risks and come up with new ideas.

Work-Life Balance: By promoting efficient work practices, productivity allows employees to complete their tasks in less time, contributing to a better work-life balance. This is important for maintaining physical and mental health, which affects performance at work.

Adaptability: A good workplace frequently exhibits flexibility. It can swiftly adjust to new procedures and technology.

The productivity and well-being are very essential for an office employee that may affect his overall mental and physical health. So, it is essential to have a better performing office for better output. There should be certain consideration and parameters for enhancing the productivity in an office space.

Aim

Investigating the spatial planning and design elements within office spaces that can enhance productivity of its users.

3. Objectives

- To understand the importance of spatial design elements on user's productivity in workspace.
- Understanding potential of spatial design elements and principals to establish parameters for productivity enhancement.
- Developing set of design recommendations for workspace to optimize user performance for maximize productivity.

4. Scope

The study will be based on analysis of the parameters undertaken for study under Spatial Planning and Design Elements of an office space.

The parameters are:

SPATIAL PLANNING	DESIGN ELEMENT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open / Close Layout • Flexible Workspaces • Movement • Way Findings • Optimal Lighting • Access to Nature • Temperature Control • Air quality • Access to Amenities • Visual Privacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Furniture • Colour • Personalization • Technology integration • Room Acoustics • Artwork

Figure 3 scope diagram

5. Limitation

Limiting the study to Spatial Planning and Design Elements of office space, the study will focus on productivity of its user groups, as impacted by its surrounding architecture.

6. Methodology

Figure 4 Methodology.

- Studying evolution of office spaces to develop parameters for critical analysis of contemporary workspace.
- Establish parameters to judge the impact of spatial design element in workspace.
- Exploring potential of established parameters on various office designs as case study.
- Comparatively analyzing work environment in offices based on set parameters.
- Recommending suitable criteria of implementation of design theories to maximize productivity.
- Conducting survey based on user experience and accumulation of the data in the form of charts.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

Our efficiency and productivity can be determined by several factors according to state of our mind and our response to the different situations-

Mood: The look and feel of an office can have a big impact on how employees feel. Improved employee happiness and morale can be attributed to a happy and productive work environment, which is facilitated by a well-designed workplace. A workplace design can enhance well-being and lower stress levels by giving staff members access to natural light and vegetation.

Decision-making: Employee decision-making may be impacted by the layout of a workplace. A well-designed workspace can produce a supportive and cooperative atmosphere that results in better decision-making.

Creativity - A well-designed office can also help to boost employee creativity. “By providing employees with a comfortable and stimulating work environment, office design can help to encourage creativity and innovation. Additionally, by providing employees with access to the tools and resources they need, office design can help to facilitate creative thinking.”

Comfort - Comfort in the workplace is a critical factor that can significantly affect employee productivity. A comfortable work environment allows employees to focus better, reduces physical strain, and minimizes distractions, leading to improved performance and efficiency.

Figure 5 emotion in office space.

The Parameters

There can be different factors that might affect productivity of an employee in an office space are as follows-

Open vs. Closed Layout: The design of office spaces has a significant impact on the productive collaboration of people. The open layout encourages teamwork and a free exchange of ideas, which creates innovation and creates camaraderie among colleagues. It encourages unplanned conversations that lead to creative ideas and a dynamic work environment. On the other hand, private spaces provide people with an ideal environment for focused work and attention. These quiet areas provide seclusion, reduce external distractions and allow employees to focus on challenging tasks undisturbed. A well-designed workplace should ideally combine private and open spaces and strike a balance between concentrated work and teamwork.

This provides a flexible space that accommodates different work styles and increases overall productivity.

Figure 6 open layout.

Figure 7 closed layout.

Optimal Lighting: We must make sure the workspace has the optimal lighting. Dim light may cause headaches, eye strain, and exhaustion. The ideal lighting is natural light, but if that isn't a possibility full spectrum lighting that mimic daylight can be a choice. To further minimize glare and shadows, give each workspace job lighting.

Figure 8 Optimal lighting.

Biophilic Design: Incorporating plants into workplace architecture has a number of benefits that are good for both employees and the atmosphere in general. Plants do increase well-being and reduce stress. Having them in the office can help reduce tension and create a more pleasant environment, promoting a calm and relaxed atmosphere. Plants do clean the

air by releasing oxygen into the atmosphere and filtering out toxins, improving productivity and cognitive performance. In addition, the presence of landscaping has been associated with increased creativity and a sense of connection with nature, which increases employee inspiration and vitality. So, the including plants in office spaces has great psychological and benefits that, in addition to aesthetic appeal, support a more positive and productive working atmosphere.

Figure 9 biophilic design.

Ergonomic Furniture: Health and comfort have always affected more from ergonomic furniture. The comfort of employees who work for long hours in the office must be given importance, from ergonomic workstations to ergonomic seats. Back injuries and neck problems, which are frequently caused by normal furniture and seating arrangements, can be prevented with adjustable furniture and ergonomics of workstations.

Employee productivity can increase, and efficiency can be increased with comfy chairs. Long work hours in the workplace include the potential to impact individuals' emotional and physical well-being. Not only will greatly comfort, lower health risks, but also it will also boost output.

Figure 10 furniture.

Noise Management: Loud noises can be distracting and have a negative effect on output of an employee. By including items that absorbs sound, such carpeting and acoustic panels, and by giving workers who require a quiet workspace a headphone. This might help in including their focus.

Figure 11 noise management.

Amenity Access: Make sure staff members have access to different facilities such as conference rooms, restrooms, and break areas. An organized workspace can boost productivity and lower stress levels.

Figure 12 access to amenities,

Encourage Movement: It is reasonable to encourage physical activity as wellbeing is about being in excellent mental and physical health. There are several methods to include movement into your wellness workplace design. Employee mobility and maximizing the use of mobile devices and cloud connection are encouraged by flexible workspace. Long lengths of time spent sitting still have been shown to harm the musculoskeletal system and raise the risk of heart disease, diabetes, strokes, high blood pressure, and increased cholesterol.

It has been seen that physical activity lessens both mental and physical health issues. So, design strategists think about ways to make better use of workplace space while also motivating staff to move around during the work.

Figure 13 encourage movement.

Wayfinding: To make it easier for staff members and guests so that they can find their way throughout the office, we should use wayfinding solutions and clear signages. This can reduce misunderstanding and confusion while increasing productivity.

Privacy Solutions: striking a balance between designating places for collaboration and privacy for concentrated work that foster communication and teamwork. It involves carefully considering the layout and plan of action to meet the security need while promoting proximity and cooperation among staff members.

Private Offices: These are enclosed areas reserved for individual employees or senior managers. They are suitable for work needing seclusion, concentration, or little distractions and give a higher level of security. Private offices are frequently located away from busy areas and typically have sturdy glass or separators for visual protection.

Open Plan Layout: this type of arrangement enhances verbal and visual engagement among employees while reducing physical barriers of collaboration and communication. They frequently consist of communal spaces or shared workstations that allow for connection and a feeling of belonging to the environment.

Partition Systems: You may divide the workplace area with partitions like moveable dividers, modular boards, and unsupported screens. These sections provide varying levels of sound and vision screening, allowing individuals or groups to enjoy private spaces while maintaining an air of openness and community.

Soundproofing: The use of efficient soundproofing and acoustic design is essential to ensure the security of office buildings. Sound-absorbing boards, acoustic materials, and suitable coverings can help reduce noise transfer across areas so that conversations or other disturbing effects are not heard.

Figure 14, privacy solution.

Flexible Workspaces: It offers a range of workspace options, which may include standing desks, lounging areas, and group workstations and many more, to promote creativity and collaboration among the employees. This gives employee the freedom to select the setting that matches their needs and tastes.

Temperature Control: It keeps the office at a reasonable temperature because highs or lows can affect focus and productivity. The optimum temperature should be set so that it is fit for maximum workers.

Personalization: Allowing employees to personalize their workspaces with photos, plants, or other personal items may help to create a sense of ownership and improve overall job satisfaction to them.

Figure 16 Personalization.

Literature Review

Title	Citation	Inferences
The work environment pilot: An experiment to determine the optimal office design for a technology company	dos Santos Accioly Lins, C. C., de Moraes Ramos-Perez, F. M., dos Anjos Pontual, A., dos Anjos Pontual, M. L., & do Nascimento, E. H. L. (2021). Digital oral radiography. In <i>Digitization in Dentistry: Clinical Applications</i> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the factors affecting productivity in an office space. How to make an office space more productive based on different office layout.
The relationship between Employees performance and office design	dos Santos Accioly Lins, C. C., de Moraes Ramos-Perez, F. M., dos Anjos Pontual, A., dos Anjos Pontual, M. L., & do Nascimento, E. H. L. (2021). Digital oral radiography. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65169-5_3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How the Customized Workspace works. How the office placement effect the wellbeing of an individual. Strategic Office Placement in Modern-Day Workspace
An Overview of the Influence of Physical Office Environments towards Employees	Kamarulzaman, N., Saleh, A. A., Hashim, S. Z., Hashim, H., & Abdul-Ghani, A. A. (2011). An overview of the influence of physical office environments towards employees. <i>Procedia Engineering</i> , 20, 262–268. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2011.11.164	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How does noise, colours, temperature effect the physical environment in an office space. Effect of physical workplace design.
Office spaces for more innovation and space efficiency	Zoltán, E. (2014). Office spaces for more innovation and space efficiency. <i>Pollack Periodica</i> , 9(2), 67–76. https://doi.org/10.1556/Pollack.9.2014.2.7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alternative office spaces for more productivity and space efficiency. use the existing office buildings more sustainable, healthier by having
The Impact of Ergonomics on Productivity in Office Buildings in Lagos, Nigeria	Kosiochukwu A. I., & Oluwatoyin A. A. (2022). The Impact of Ergonomics on Productivity in Office Buildings in Lagos, Nigeria. <i>Iconic Research and Engineering Journals</i> , 6(3), 51–56.	Requirement of correct ergonomics and how they can impact our productivity.
The impact of office layout on productivity	Hameed, A. (Comsats I. of I. T., & Amjad, S. (Comsats I. of I. T. (2009). Impact of Office Design on Employees' Productivity: A Case study of Banking. <i>Journal of Public Affairs, Administration and Management</i> , 3(1), 1–13.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How office design have evolved Office design post covid and how it effects productivity
A Comparative Study on The Impacts of Open Plan and Closed Office Layout Towards	Muzaffar, P. N. A., Mohamed Noor, N., & Mahmud, S. A. (2020). A Comparative Study on The Impacts of Open Plan and Closed Office Layout Towards. 6, 49–58.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Study of open and closed layout How these two determines the productivity of an individual.

		more productive
The work environment pilot: An experiment to determine the optimal office design for a technology company	Pitchforth, J., Nelson-White, E., Van Den Helder, M., & Oosting, W. (2020). The work environment pilot: An experiment to determine the optimal office design for a technology company. In <i>PLoS ONE</i> (Vol. 15, Issue 5). https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0232943	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges faced in office design. Discussing the different type of modern office layout. comparing four different office designs (Open-plan, Zoned open-plan, Activity based, and Team offices)
Workplace productivity and office type: an evaluation of office occupier differences based on age and gender	Haynes, B., Suckley, L., & Nunnington, N. (2017). Workplace productivity and office type: An evaluation of office occupier differences based on age and gender. In <i>Journal of Corporate Real Estate</i> (Vol. 19, Issue 2). https://doi.org/10.1108/JCRE-11-2016-0037	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Differences between office occupiers' perceived productivity based on gender, age and office type. evaluation of the impact of office layout on office productivity.
Well-being as a tool to improve productivity in existing office space: Case study in Alexandria, Egypt	Hamadah, M., ElSeragy, A., & ElDeeb, S. (2023). Well-being as a tool to improve productivity in existing office space: Case study in Alexandria, Egypt. <i>F1000Research</i> , 12, 1–46. https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.133199.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Showing thermal comfort, and natural daylight influence productivity.

III. EVOLUTION OF OFFICE SPACE

The Evolution of Office Space

The evolution of office design is a fascinating journey that reflects changes in technology, work practices, and societal norms. With time the offices have evolved according to the need and requirement of the employees.

The First Modern Office

The first dedicated office building for centralized administrative work was established in 1726 in London, England. The office structure is the former admiralty (Ripley structure). Constructed to manage the abundance of documentation produced by the Royal Navy, it featured conference rooms and the Admiralty Board Room, which remains operational to this day.

Figure 17 first modern office

Taylorism Office

The emergence of open-plan workplaces in a Taylorism age when office layout reflects hierarchy and status may be seen in Frank Lloyd Wright's Larkin Building, one of the first modern office buildings.

A result of hierarchical labour management, offices had inflexible floor plans with rows of desks occupied by secretarial employees. Repeated open-plan spaces were produced by long, thin floor layouts that were designed to maximize natural light.

Figure 18 Taylorism office

The Streamlined Office

Frank Lloyd Wright created the effective open-plan office building known as the Johnson Wax Building with efficiency in mind rather than manufacturing. Wright compensates for the lack of outside interaction with new elements like cork ceilings, cozy spaces, and bright lighting. It increases productivity and saves time by utilizing technology, streamlining processes, and getting rid of duplication.

Figure 19 Streamlined Offices

Burolandschaft

Frank Lloyd Wright created the effective open-plan office Burolandschaft, which translates to "office landscape" from German, is a more organic and socially democratic workplace layout that encourages human connection and makes use of plants as screen separators. It disrupts the rigid structures of previous office layouts.

Figure 20, Burolandschaft

The Action Office

In response to the growing need for privacy in the workplace, Action Office is created. This translates into low-divider, modular office furniture and adaptable workstations.

Figure 21 The Action Office

The Cubicle farm

The idea of the "Action Office" deteriorates to a very dystopian extreme: the notorious "Cubicle Farm," with its tall barriers and contained areas, is a vivid example of a financial attitude that completely disregards the well-being of its employees.

Figure 22 The Cubicle Farm.

The Virtual Office

Businesses may function effectively without incurring the capital costs associated with owning or renting a physical office because of the combination of services, space, and technology that a virtual office. It serves startups, remote workers, independent contractors, and even well-established businesses looking for affordable solutions.

Figure 23 The Virtual Office

The Dot-com Bubble

Dot Com titans, who are concerned with blurring the lines between work and pleasure as well as between people and space, are adopting a shortened version of the open plan's layout, which is becoming more and more popular.

Figure 24, The Dot-Com Office

The Barrier-free office

Digital nomadism and remote employment have become the new standard in the new millennium. While gaming rooms and beanbags are preferred over "all work and no play" in the office, coffee shops and hotel lobbies frequently serve as informal workspaces.

Figure 25, The Barrier Free Office

The Conventional Offices

Office design nowadays prioritizes employee comfort and welfare with an emphasis on biophilia and natural light, drawing inspiration from homes more and more. Office design is finally eschewing the "one size fits all" mantra in favor of activity-based workspaces that accommodate a variety of working habits, as opposition to open plan layouts grows.

Figure 26 Conventional Offices

2. Contemporary Office Spaces

- Contemporary office design draws inspiration from the aesthetics and design concepts of the present period. It evolves over time, reflecting the prevailing styles and trends.
- Contemporary offices full fills the need of the employer according to his requirement.
- There are several types office spaces used today with their own specialty.

These components of office design largely reference mid-century modern models, which offer comfort and ageless flexibility through:

- neat lines
- organic materials
- Visual forms
- vibrant hues
- cozy chairs
- Indoor-outdoor ideas

The Cellular Offices

A common corridor connects the single or multi-person workplaces that make up cellular offices, which are often arranged along a building's external wall.

In workplaces with many people, workstations or up to six desks are standard. Individual offices are especially good for jobs that need a lot of discretion or very concentrated care.

Figure 27, The Cellular Offices

Group Offices

Typically, group offices have up to 25 desks or workstations available. They are located close to windows and clearly separated from each other by walls or moveable space-structuring elements.

Similar to multi-person offices, group offices work best for close-knit teams and companies where employees must be able to cover for one another immediately.

Figure 28, the Group Offices

Combi Offices

Open-plan and cubicle workplace components are frequently combined in combination offices. Each work cubicle, which are arranged around a common area with kitchenettes, file departments, chat areas, and other facilities, usually houses one worker. Glass walls and doors separate the cubicles from the common area. Combo offices are ideal for businesses that require a lot of space for (spontaneous) collaboration in addition to a large percentage of focused individual work.

Figure 29, The Combi Offices

Open Offices Plan

Office workstations are arranged in an orderly and spatial manner in open-plan offices, which have floor plans of 400 square meters or more and can be divided with partition walls. Traditional open-plan workstations are especially suitable for companies experiencing significant organizational transformation.

Modern Open Offices Plans

Modern open-plan designs, sometimes referred to as "open spaces," are not a distinct kind of space design; rather, they are a combination of several office spaces. Workers may choose the workplace or common area that best fits their current duties by mixing several work and communication zones.

Figure 31 Modern Office plan

IV. CASE STUDIES

1. Google Office, Moscow

Figure 32 Google Office plan

Project Type: Office Building

Location: 7 Balchug St. Moscow, Russian Federation
 Architect: Evolution Design
 Client: Google
 Floor Area: 2600 m²

- *Entrance/Reception*
- *Tech Talk*
- *Cafeteria*
- *Meeting Area*
- *Informal Discussion Area*
- *Office*
- *Private Office*
- *Magic Forest/Micro Kitchen*

The office has a centralized organization with services in the centre and everything else around. These considerations usually revolve around creating dynamic, collaborative, and comfortable work environments that foster creativity, productivity, and employee well-being.

The workstation have been organized along the windows for optimal lighting, the workstation does not have any privacy barriers creating a open : closed layout ratio to 3:1. The meeting rooms have been arranged equally throughout the office with informal areas have been placed along with the meeting rooms,

Workstations

Figure 33, Google workstation plan

Figure 34, Google Workstation

The open workstation have been provided improve the interaction of the employee while giving the enough area acting as privacy barrier. The storage desk has been provided on the side of the table.

Employee Training Areas

Figure 36, google training plan

Figure 37, Google training area.

Separate training area have been provided away from workstations to train its employees and have interactive sessions. This provides separate space to the employees training and other recreational activities.

Recreational Areas

Figure 40, Google Recreational plan.

Figure 35, Google canteen

Figure 38, Google recreational 2.

Figure 41, Google Meeting Rooms

Figure 39, Magic Forest

These interactive spaces have been made for the employee to relax and have their leisure time. This area includes the canteen, specially designed magic forest area.

Meeting Rooms

There are different typology of formal meeting room provided in this office for team and personal interaction, promoting collation between the employees.

Figure 42, Google office images

2. Headquarter Microsoft, Vienna

- Data Highway
- Interactive Circulation Furniture
- Meeting Room
- Open Workspace

- Workstation has been provided along the windows for natural lighting.
- The office has a centralized core with services in the centre and everything else around.

- The core is surrounded by meeting rooms on three side and leisure room on one side providing good circulation for the employee.
- The different function and amenities have been provided on different floor giving them a friendly environment.
- Modern technologies are integrated throughout the facility to support staff and increase efficiency.

Workstations

Figure 45, Microsoft workstation plan.

The open workstation provides interaction of the employee while promoting the concept of flexible workspace. The workstation has been provided with low barrier for giving the feeling of privacy. The workstation have been placed along the windows for amount of lighting.

Recreational Areas

These interactive spaces have been made for the employee to relax and have their leisure time. The slide provided in second floor to first floor is the key attraction.

Figure 43, Microsoft First Floor

- **Project Type:** Office Building
- **Location:** Am Europl. 3, 1120 Wien, Austria
- **Architect:** ARGE KOOP/INNOCAD
- **Client:** Microsoft
- **Floor Area:** 4500 m²

Figure 46. Microsoft workstation

Figure 44, Microsoft Second Floor

Figure 47, Microsoft recreational area.

Training Areas

The training areas is provided on the ground floor and can be used for the common gathering and recreational purpose according to the need of the individual.

Figure 48 Training area

Figure 49, Training

Meeting Areas

The Meeting are provided with the capacity of 4 and 14 with the multi-use purpose.

Figure 50, Microsoft meeting room

Figure 51, Microsoft Austria Interior

Adobe Campus, Noida

Ground floor plan.

2. Architects: SWBI Architects Pvt. Ltd
3. Project: Adobe Campus
4. Location: Sector 132, Noida, India
5. Site Area (sq ft & sq m): 7 acres land - 28,322 sqm

Figure 53, Adobe Typical Plan

- Workstation has been provided along the windows for natural lighting.
- The office has its core on either side of the building and two atriums and collaboration space in the core.
- The meeting rooms have been provided surrounded by the workstation so it easily accessible its employees.

Figure 55, Adobe Meeting Room

Figure 54, Atrium

Figure 56, Adobe Recreational Area

Cafeteria

The open workstation have been provided improve the interaction of the employee while giving the enough area acting as privacy barrier.

Workstation

The workstation was initially arranged in a closed layout with ample of privacy, in a circular core form. But later kept side by side, closed from three side and open from one side.

Recreational Area

The Recreational area has been provided around the Atrium and staircase for collaboration and spend leisure time. The Communication walkway pass on both the side of the atrium.

Meeting Areas

Figure 57, Adobe Meeting Area

The meeting rooms have been arranged equally along with the workstation. It also serves as collaborative or group work area along with the offices of the seniors.

Figure 58, Adobe, Noida

Indian Glycol Office, Noida

Figure 59, Ground Floor Plan

Figure 60, First Floor Plan

- Project Type: Office Building
- Location: Sector 126, Noida
- Architect: Morphogenesis
- Client: India Glycol Site
- Area: 2,15,280 Sq. Ft. (20,200 Sq. Mt.)
- Workstation has been provided along the windows for natural lighting.
- The office has a centralized courtyard with the green spaces to cater in harsh climate.
- The building promotes the healthy work culture for its employee.

Workstation

Closed and private workspace along the windows. Short heighted barriers are provided to create the feeling of privacy among the employees.

Meeting Rooms

They are provided separately away from the workstation of the employees. They parallel and circular sitting arrangement according to the need, they can also be used as the collaborative space for group work.

Recreational Area

Provided rarely, can be found in between workstation and meeting room. Can be used for leisure.

Workstation

Apart from the workstation closed offices provided near the workstation for better office movement and Privacy.

Table 1, Comparative study of Case studies

DESIGN ELEMENT	GOOGLE OFFICE, MOSCOW	HEADQUARTER MICROSOFT, VIENNA	ADOBE CAMPUS, NOIDA	INDIAN GLYCOL OFFICE, NOIDA
Open Layout	*	*		
Closed Layout	*	*	*	*
Flexible Workspace	*	*	*	
Movement	*	*	*	*
Way Finding			*	
Optimal Lighting	*	*	*	
Access to Nature				*
Temp. Control	*	*	*	*
Access to Amenities	*	*	*	*
Visual privacy		*	*	*
Furniture	*	*	*	*
Personalization	*	*	*	*
Room Acoustics	*	*	*	*

Table 2, Inferences of the studies

Location	GOOGLE MOSCOW, RUSSIA	MICROSOFT VIENNA, AUSTRIA	ADOBE OFFICE, NOIDA	INDIAN GLYCOL OFFICE, NOIDA
Inferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating a warm, welcoming and relaxed environment for the employees. Employee workstations are classic open desk arrangement. Casual and formal meeting space near the work area. Amenities are distributed equally throughout the plan. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing natural lighting throughout the building. Flexible work area allowing the employees to choose the environment they want to work in. Casual and formal meeting space near the work area. Amenities are evenly distributed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing collaborative and private workspace for its employees and providing healthy environment. The meeting rooms have been distributed equally throughout the building. The services for Kitchen is in Stilt level (below ground) like Service Entry, Washing Area, Storage, etc. Amenities like games and cafeteria have been provided on the ground floor. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing natural lighting throughout the building. Visual and physical connection with nature. Less casual meeting area inside the office space. The office does not provide much area for other recreational activities. Can be called a traditional office with modern design.

V. OPINION SURVEY

Opinion Survey

Table 3, The Opinion Survey 17 employee of IT sector

Table 5, Satisfaction with open office layout

Table 4, Satisfaction with closed office layout

Table 6, Satisfaction with optimal lighting

Table 7, Satisfaction with Ergonomic of Furniture

Table 8, Access to Amenities

Table 9, Noise management

Table 10, Satisfaction with privacy

Table 11, Satisfaction in moment

Table 12, Satisfaction with temperature control

Table 13, Satisfaction with flexible workspace

Table 14, Opinion on personalization of work space

Table 15, showing users feeling on different parameters.

VI. CONCLUSION & RECOMENDATION

1. Conclusion

The research concludes that architecture forms a very crucial role in enhancing the user experience, well-being and productivity in office buildings through the architectural typology of interactive spaces. In this era where people spend there most of the time of their day without any social interaction in the office focusing on their work, there is a tremendous need for enhancing the working space and layout in offices for users' wellbeing. Architecture becomes a physical aspect that represents the various parameters affecting the user's perception of working. The research paper focus on the various parameters that effect the productivity of an individual in an office space.

2. General Recommendation

Spatial arrangement

A hybrid office layout is ideal for enhancing social contact between users and offering greater flexibility in social and professional settings. It comprises of open-plan offices and activity-based offices with more interactive spaces and activity-based zones. Conversely, a closed arrangement emphasizes an employee's concentrated labour to yield the highest possible productivity. However, maintaining the open to close ratio of 3:1 is very necessary. In workplaces with hybrid plans, the ideal configuration is: -

- Set up the enclosed workplace on the floor plate's edge.
- An atrium in the middle of the city with various leisure options

- To break up the monotony of the room, there should be informal places interspersed with open workstations across the floor plate.

Circulation

- All the spaces should be connected by an open circulation area, since this improves mobility, fosters social contact, and creates an air of openness for everyone.
- It is easy to find this kind of circulation in activity-based and open-plan offices.

Building Envelope

- Using architectural features like a centrally located atrium with a skylight that gives natural light throughout the areas, natural light may be obtained.
- Natural light is given increasing priority in offices since it serves to enhance users' well-being.
- The building's fully glass façade, facing the right direction, aids in letting in natural light.

Acoustics

- Sound-absorbing materials are utilized in floors, ceilings, and furniture to manage how sound interacts with the physical space of the workplace.
- To reduce the amount of sound waves transmitted, soft cushioned roofs are used.
- Various areas are designed to offer sound isolation.

6. Hameed, A. (Comsats I. of I. T., & Amjad, S. (Comsats I. of I. T. (2009). Impact of Office Design on Employees' Productivity : A Case study of Banking. *Journal of Public Affairs, Administration and Management*, 3(1), 1–13
7. Muzaffar, P. N. A., Mohamed Noor, N., & Mahmud, S. A. (2020). a Comparative Study on the Impacts of Open Plan and Closed Office Layout Towards. 6, 49–58.
8. Thomsen A., Schultmann F., Kohler N. Deconstruction, demolition and destruction, *Building Research and Information*, Vol. 39, No. 4, 2011, pp. 327–332.
9. Schriefer A. E. Workplace strategy, what it is and why you should care, *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, Vol. 7, No. 3, 2005, pp. 222–233
10. M. Asselineau and A. Gaulupeau (2013) Assessing the Acoustics of Offices: A case of Standardization [Online] Available at: <https://asa.scitation.org/doi/pdf/10.1121/1.4799358> [Accessed on 26th November, 2020].
11. Laestadius (2009) The Proactive Approach-Is it worthwhile? A prospective Controlled Ergonomic Intervention Study in Office Workers [Online] Available at: https://journals.lww.com/joem/Abstract/2009/10000/The_Proactive_Approach_Is_It_Worthwhile__A.2.aspx [Accessed on 23rd May, 2021].
12. Cena, K. (2001) Thermal Comfort and Behavioural Strategies in Office-Buildings Located in Hot Climates [Online] Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306456501000523> [Accessed on 23rd May, 2021]

REFERENCES

1. dos Santos Accioly Lins, C. C., de Moraes Ramos-Perez, F. M., dos Anjos Pontual, A., dos Anjos Pontual, M. L., & do Nascimento, E. H. L. (2021). Digital oral radiography. In *Digitization in Dentistry: Clinical Applications*.
2. dos Santos Accioly Lins, C. C., de Moraes Ramos-Perez, F. M., dos Anjos Pontual, A., dos Anjos Pontual, M. L., & do Nascimento, E. H. L. (2021). Digital oral radiography. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65169-5_3
3. Kamarulzaman, N., Saleh, A. A., Hashim, S. Z., Hashim, H., & Abdul-Ghani, A. A. (2011). An overview of the influence of physical office environments towards employees. *Procedia Engineering*, 20, 262–268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2011.11.164>
4. Zoltán, E. (2014). Office spaces for more innovation and space efficiency. *Pollack Periodica*, 9(2), 67–76. <https://doi.org/10.1556/Pollack.9.2014.2.7>
5. Kosisochukwu A, I., & Oluwatoyin A, A. (2022). The Impact of Ergonomics on Productivity in Office Buildings in Lagos, Nigeria. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 6(3), 51–56.